

Fermat's Least Time Equivalent to Information Minimization/ Statistical Equilibrium?

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Fermat's least time principle may be applied to reflection of light from a stationary or moving mirror and refraction to name three examples. The idea behind two ray problems (with the assumption of straight line motion between points which is already an idea of Fermat's principle) is to express total time in terms of x , the position at which the incident ray hits the mirror or medium surface which is assumed to lie along the x axis. To do this one assumes a length L along the mirror or medium surface such that $y=Y$ for the incident and reflected/refracted rays. One then varies with respect to x .

There are two things one may note about the minimization/extremization. First distance / (c/n) is the time for each ray with n , the index of refraction, possibly changing for each. Distance is $\sqrt{Y^2 + x^2}$ and $\sqrt{Y^2 + (L-x)^2}$ in a reflection problem for example. Thus $d(\text{time})/dx = 0$ yields $\text{weight}_1 x / \text{hypotenuse}_1 = \text{weight}_2 (L-x) / \text{hypotenuse}_2$ which is equivalent to a conservation law and may be extended to represent conservation of momentum in the x direction. Fermat's principle, however, goes beyond this idea we argue.

The second point we wish to make is that for the case of reflection from a stationary mirror one really finds the ratio $x / (L-x)$. If this is not 1, then one requires more information than if it is 1. For instance, assume one knows the angle of incidence, but that the angle of reflection differs. Then one needs a pair of information pieces namely the angle of incidence and that of reflection. If the two are the same, only one piece of information is required. This we argue is the ultimate result of Fermat's least time principle applied to reflection from a stationary mirror.

This idea of minimization of information, however, seems to apply to the equilibrium treatment of an ideal gas. For example, two particles with energy e_1 and e_2 and amounts $f(e_1)$, $f(e_2)$ collide such that the resulting e_3 , e_4 satisfies $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$. Thus there is the most loss of information allowed by constraints i.e. the maximization of entropy. If this is the case, then reflection from a stationary mirror seems to follow the same underlying principle as statistical equilibrium instead of representing classical mechanics which is then in turn used to create a statistical mechanical theory for many particles.

Two Ray Fermat's Principle and Conservation

In (1) it is stated that Snell's law of refraction may be derived using conservation of x momentum using the idea that momentum p in a vacuum becomes p_n in a medium. With this assumption:

$$P n_1 \sin(A) = p n_2 \sin(B) \quad ((1)) \text{ where } n_1, n_2 \text{ are the two indices of refraction and } A \text{ and } B$$

The angle of incidence and refraction measured from the normal.

Setting $n_1 = n_2$ give $A = B$ which is the result for reflection from a stationary mirror. We argue, however, that an assumption is made namely that the y component of momentum of the

reflected ray is the negative of the incoming y component. It is possible mathematically to have $p_1 \sin(A) = p_2 \sin(B)$ with p_1 and p_2 different and A and B different.

Fermat's principle for reflection from a stationary mirror, however, does lead to the angle of reflection equaling the angle of incidence and also yields conservation of momentum in the x direction. Thus we argue that Fermat's principle of least time yields conservation of x momentum, but the converse does not necessarily hold. To see this, consider a ray starting at $x=0, y=Y$ and hitting the mirror at $x=x$ and $y=0$. It then moves to $y=Y$ and $x=L-x$. The total time is found using $\text{distance}/c = \text{time}$:

$$\text{Total time} = \sqrt{Y^2 + x^2}/c + \sqrt{Y^2 + (L-x)^2}/c \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{Thus } d/dx \text{ total time} = 0 = x / \{c \sqrt{Y^2 + x^2}\} + (L-x) / \{c \sqrt{Y^2 + (L-x)^2}\} \quad ((3))$$

Or $\sin(A)/c = \sin(B)/c$ so $A=B$.

One may note that ((3)) is of the form of a conservation law in the x direction i.e. $\sin(A) = \sin(B)$. Multiplying by p and assuming that it does not change for the reflected ray from a stationary mirror one has $p \sin(A) = p \sin(B)$ or momentum conservation in the x direction. For two ray problems such as reflection from a constantly moving mirror and refraction one has a similar form to ((3)) i.e. a conservation in the x direction result. Thus Fermat's principle for two rays implies an x direction conservation, but the converse does not necessarily hold.

Loss of Information

In the above treatment of Fermat's least time principle the first derivative $d \text{ time} / dx$ happens to yield a conservation law in the x direction. We argue, however, that the main objective of Fermat's principle is to find the ratio:

$$x / (L-x) \quad ((4))$$

This is equivalent to finding $\sin(A)$ in terms of $\sin(B)$. The point we make for reflection from a stationary mirror is that Fermat's least time principle is really a least information principle. The fact that $x=L-x$ i.e. $A=B$ means only one piece of information instead of two is required. In other words, if one knows x , one knows $L-x$ or if one knows A one knows B . This does not follow from conservation of momentum in the x direction because if one knows A and p incident, one does not know that $p_y \text{ reflected} = -p_y \text{ incident}$. This is a separate assumption it seems.

Statistical Theory

We argue that applying Fermat's principle to reflection from a stationary mirror has the form of minimizing time, but really minimizes information. This, we argue, is no different from finding an extremum for entropy in a classical gas equilibrium problem. For a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, one also seeks a minimization of information subject to physical constraints existing i.e. conservation

of energy in two body interactions and a two particle collision probability proportional to $f(e_1)f(e_2)$ where $f(e_i)$ is the number of particles with energy e_i . In such a case one has;

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \text{ and } f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((5))$$

Any e_3, e_4 pair that satisfies conservation of energy is a possible two body collision outcome so there is a loss of information. In such a problem there is also the concept of temperature which does not seem to appear in the Fermat's least time principle applied to reflection from a stationary mirror. Nevertheless we argue that the same underlying statistical principle of a loss of information applies to both. Thus reflection from a stationary mirror which at first might appear to be a classical mechanical type of problem may really be a statistical mechanical problem. In other words statistical mechanics may not be a theory developed as an approximation to many body classical mechanics, but may be an underlying idea linked to information. We note that the idea of information playing an underlying and fundamental role in physics has already been suggested by Deutsch and Marletto in (2).

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that Fermat's minimal time principle for two ray systems (reflection from a stationary and constantly moving mirror and refraction) leads to a conservation law in the x direction, but implies more than this conservation. In particular, we examine reflection from a stationary mirror and suggest that the minimization of time with respect to x (the point at which the incident ray hits the mirror with $L-x$ being the "other length" is really a calculation of the ratio of x and $L-x$. This in turn is linked to information. In particular it is found that $x/(L-x)$ is 1 so only one piece of information x or alternatively A the angle of incidence is needed. We argue that in this case Fermat's minimal time principle really finds a minimum of information which is a statistical idea pertaining to equilibrium. It is similar to the idea of maximizing entropy. Thus we suggest that instead of considering reflection of light from a stationary mirror as a classical mechanical problem, it may actually be a statistical one with the underlying idea being the minimization of information.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Snell%27s_law
2. Deutsch, D. and Marletto, C. Constructor Theory of Information (Proceedings of the Royal Society A Feb. 8, 2015 doi 10.1098/rspa.2014.0540
<https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/10.1098/rspa.2014.0540>